

APPLICATION OF THE IMMOBILISATION METHOD TO INCREASE THE STABILITY OF ENZYMES

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Relevance: It should be noted that enzymes have reciprocal and opposite processes, which disrupts the stability of substances in combination with the second component. There are several ways to avoid this: protecting active substances from acidic environments; prolonging the release of the active destructive substance; and creating a multi-layered dosage form with programmable release profiles for individual dosage selection. The combination of ibuprofen with serratiopeptidase, an enzyme with anti-inflammatory and fibrinolytic effects, can reduce side effects. However, the low stability of serratiopeptidase in the gastric environment requires the development of innovative approaches.

In order to justify our selection, we conduct research with model drug mixtures of various combinations and different coating (immobilisation) methods to create a stable drug mixture with subsequent transfer of the composition into a rational dosage form.

Aim of the study: To justify and conduct preliminary experimental research on a combined drug based on serratiopeptidase and ibuprofen using immobilisation technologies aimed at increasing the stability and bioavailability of the active substances.

Materials and methods: Three delivery forms were used as research objects: MKTS (calcium alginate matrix), MKTS Paxta (with stabiliser added), and Entrotsel (purified complex). The stability and kinetics of active substance release were analysed using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with the Farm HPLC system (DDD: 227, 223, 232 nm; FLD: Ex = 230 nm, Em = 460 nm). The theoretical part of the study included an analysis of the prospects for using chitosan as a carrier, taking into account its physicochemical and pharmaco-technological properties.

Results: To create a stable medicinal model mixture, studies were conducted to justify the selection of various combinations and different coating (immobilisation) methods. To develop a method for quantifying the active ingredients – serratiopeptidase and ibuprofen – in the mixture before and after coating (encapsulation) of the enzyme, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with a spectrophotometric detector. According to HPLC data, it was found that MKTS Paxta (locally produced) and Entrotsel (with added stabilisers) provide a more stable release of serratiopeptidase and ibuprofen compared to the basic calcium alginate form. In particular, there is a delayed and controlled release of active substances, which indicates the potential effectiveness of these delivery systems. Theoretical analysis confirms that chitosan complexes have a number of advantages, including resistance to acidic environments, mucoadhesiveness, and the ability to increase bioavailability.

Conclusion: Preliminary experimental data combined with theoretical analysis confirm the promise of developing a combined drug based on serratiopeptidase and ibuprofen using innovative delivery matrices. The most optimal forms appear to be MKTS Paxta with the addition of stabilisers

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or based on chitosan. The results open up opportunities for further research and development of an effective prolonged-release dosage form.